

MUHIDDIN RAKHIMOV HOUSE MUSEUM**Mirkhakimova Feruza Kholdorjonovna****University of Business and Science,****Department of Social Sciences, Acting Associate Professor,****Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in History.****mirhakimovaferuza7@gmail.com****ORCID:0009-0004-4333-8295****<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20785032>****ARTICLE INFO**Received: 16th June 2026

Accepted: 18th June 2026

Online: 20th June 2026

KEYWORDS

Mukhiddin Rakhimov, pottery art, house museum, applied art, Rakhimov dynasty, exposition, cultural heritage, master-apprentice tradition, artistic technique, archaeological findings

ABSTRACT

This article discusses the life and creative activity of the renowned potter, scholar, and art historian Muhiddin Rakhimov, the establishment of his house museum, and the rich cultural heritage preserved within it. It also highlights the pottery traditions of the Rakhimov dynasty and the ongoing creative and scientific work carried out by its successors. The composition of the museum exhibition, its unique exhibits, and their scientific as well as educational significance are analyzed.

Introduction. Folk applied art in Uzbekistan, particularly pottery, has an ancient history and is considered an important component of national culture. The development of this art form is closely associated with renowned masters and their creative heritage. The Mukhiddin Rakhimov House Museum, located in the city of Tashkent, is one of the places that embodies such a rich heritage. This museum not only reflects the history of the development of pottery art but also plays an important role in educating the younger generation in the spirit of national values.

The house museum of the famous Tashkent potter Mukhiddin Rakhimov (1903–1985) is located on Odil Mukhtorov Street in the Kukcha district of Tashkent. Mukhiddin Rakhimov was a scholar, a technologist of pottery, the founder of the Uzbek vocational pottery school, and a representative of the fourth generation of potters. For more than forty years, he worked as a senior researcher at the Institute of Art History of the Republic. He conducted research on pottery artifacts from the Kushan and Timurid periods. He thoroughly studied the traditional artistic techniques of pottery in Samarkand, Bukhara, Tashkent, and the Fergana Valley. He authored several books and dozens of articles on the history of pottery, the technology of producing and processing ceramic items, as well as the interpretation of various symbols and artistic images in pottery.

He created numerous remarkable works. Many outstanding pieces produced within the Tashkent pottery school are currently preserved in some of the world's finest museums, including the Hermitage Museum in Saint Petersburg and the Museum of Oriental Art in Moscow. His bowls and vases often depict flocks of mythical birds symbolizing peace and

prosperity, intricate geometric patterns, or stylized Arabic inscriptions, alongside images of fish, which have long symbolized wealth and happiness.

After the death of his father, the renowned artist and potter Akbar Rakhimov established a private house museum in 1994 at his own expense [1; 46]. The museum consists of two exhibitions: M. Rakhimov's workshop and an exhibition of works by the Rakhimov dynasty [2; 103]. The museum houses M. Rakhimov's personal belongings, books, and artistic works. It also displays archaeological findings brought by him from various expeditions.

Akbar Rakhimov is considered the sixth generation of the potter dynasty and is recognized as an Honored Artist of the Republic of Uzbekistan, an academician, and a highly skilled potter and researcher worldwide [3; 181]. His works have been successfully exhibited at international exhibitions and fairs and are preserved in renowned museums around the world. Akbar has mastered the technique of glazing ceramic vessels with alkaline glaze.

Mukhiddin Rakhimov's grandson, Alisher, has held numerous exhibitions in Uzbekistan, Japan, Germany, and France. Natural talent, a productive environment, years of study, and diligence enabled him to earn the honorable title of "master." He works in the polished pottery style of the Kushan period and the blue-glazed Timurid ceramic tradition. He also conducts experiments on restoring 5th-century carved pottery from Tashkent and creates a number of works based on the Kashgar style.

Today, both Akbar Rakhimov and Alisher Rakhimov live in the house that has been turned into a museum. Through the efforts of the Rakhimov family, the "Master–Apprentice" pottery school was established in Tashkent in 2005 [182]. At this school, Akbar and Alisher Rakhimov share their knowledge and skills with those interested in pottery.

In the hospitable Rakhimov household, all generations of potters remember Muhiddin Rakhimov's words as a legacy: "Every product is made from clay." However, one should not forget that a creator must not only sincerely love it but also help it take the necessary form.

The Mukhiddin Rakhimov House Museum is not only a place that preserves historical and cultural heritage but also an important spiritual and educational center serving the comprehensive upbringing of the younger generation. Through the exhibits collected in this museum, visitors become closely acquainted with the ancient roots of pottery art, its stages of development, and the aesthetic views of the Uzbek people.

In particular, the workshop environment in the museum plays a significant role for young people, where practical activities increase their interest in craftsmanship and help develop such important qualities as patience, diligence, and creativity. The "master–apprentice" tradition continued by the Rakhimov dynasty serves as an essential factor in passing national craftsmanship from generation to generation.

Furthermore, exhibitions, master classes, and scientific meetings held in the museum broaden the worldview of young people and educate them in the spirit of respect for national values. Muhiddin Rakhimov's scientific and creative heritage serves as an important source not only for art enthusiasts but also for researchers, playing a significant role in studying both the theoretical and practical aspects of pottery art.

From this perspective, the Muhiddin Rakhimov House Museum is a unique place that harmoniously combines history, art, and education, playing an invaluable role in preserving, developing, and passing national culture on to future generations.

Conclusion. The Muhiddin Rakhimov House Museum is an important scientific and cultural source for studying folk applied art and the history of pottery. Through this place, not only Rakhimov's rich creative heritage but also the formation and development of an entire pottery school are revealed. The museum's activities play a significant role in educating the younger generation in the spirit of respect for national values, love for art, and creativity. The continuation of traditions by the Rakhimov dynasty serves as an important factor in transmitting this art form to future generations.

References:

- 1.Филкенъштейн И. Инновационный потенциал мемориальных музеев для развития туристической индустрии Узбекистан. : Диссертация на соискание доктора философии (PhD) по историческим наукам. – Тошкент, 2024. – С. 46.
- 2.Исмаилова Ж., Левтеева Л. Музеи Узбекистана – Т. «Очун», 2020. -С.103
- 3.Исмаилова Ж., Левтеева Л. Музеи, галереи, арт – центры Ташкента. – Т. «Фан ва технология», 2017. -С. 181
- 4.Исмаилова Ж., Левтеева Л. Музеи, галереи, арт – центры Ташкента. – Т. «Фан ва технология», 2017. -С. 182

